

THE INCREASING NEED FOR CONTINUOUS SPIRITUAL EDUCATION AND ITS SOCIAL IMPORTANCE IN THE NEW STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the socio-philosophical research of the musical heritage factor in the implementation of continuous spiritual education in New Uzbekistan, the possibilities of using examples of musical heritage to increase the effectiveness of the continuous spiritual education system, the future tasks of the musical heritage factor in the process of continuous spiritual education studied. The socio-philosophical and conceptual aspects of the continuous spiritual education system are also analyzed.

Key words: continuous spiritual education, musical heritage, socio-philosophical factor, education, dynamics, harmonization, social state, systemic-functional analysis, theoretical-methodological basis, development, social value, cultural context.

INTRODUCTION. Today, in the modern conditions of Uzbekistan, spirituality, enlightenment, and education, like all other fields, need innovations. In Europe, South Korea, Japan, China, Russia, there are hundreds of organizations, foundations, and associations dealing with scientific strategies of youth education. Studying their experience, bringing modern technologies and using them for the purposes of educating young people in the spirit of the national ideal is one of the important requirements of educational modernization.

In particular, the formation of a healthy outlook among young people, including reading skills, the development of the culture of rational use of Internet and information communication technologies, the strengthening of their ideological immunity against ideological and informational attacks, the content and essence of the complex geopolitical and ideological-ideological processes taking place in the world conducting ideological struggle against all kinds of threats, terrorism, religious extremism, fanaticism, separatism, human trafficking, mass culture, drug business and other threats; - development of a complex system of measures aimed at eliminating such situations as childishness, neglect of moral values and education of young people, wide promotion of the national idea among representatives of all nationalities and peoples and social classes living in our regions are important tasks.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Wide use of examples of musical heritage in the implementation of continuous spiritual education in society and through this, scientific researches on the development of axiological attitude of young people to the national musical heritage, reform of the pedagogical process on the national musical heritage and its preservation, scientific research on determining the axiological attitude to the national musical heritage practical tasks D. Karomatli, T. Levin, Y. Elsner, E. Abdulin, YE. Bodina, O. Bochkareva, E. Burzina, N. Ivanov, L. Koval, V. Rajnikov, A. Rapatskaya, S. Bulatov, Researched by scientists such as B. Azimov, S. Annamuratova, O. Vasilchenko, Sh. Janaydarov, F. Joraev, D. Kamolova, H. Nurmatov, F. Khalilov, A. Hasanov. Also, the history, theory, characteristics of Uzbek classical musical heritage, folklore songs, R. Abdullaev, S. Begmatov, T. Vizgo, O.

Ibrohimov, F. Karomatov, I. Rajabov, T. Gafurbekov, B. Kadirov, Covered in the works of M. Kadirov, E. Fayzullaev.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. As a result of the wide-ranging reforms and creative works being implemented in our country, the way of thinking and worldview of our people is changing. In our country, the importance of the life-giving idea "From national revival to national rise" is increasing more and more in the establishment of a legal state and civil society. Despite the important work being carried out in this regard, a number of systemic problems remain, which hinder the effectiveness of spiritual and educational reforms in the process of social, economic and political reforms. In particular, there is no integrated system for the organization of spiritual-educational processes, insufficient organizational-practical and scientific-research work is being carried out to protect our people, especially young people, from spiritual threats. In this direction, state organizations, civil society institutions, mass media and social cooperation of the private sector has not been established effectively.

In order to eliminate these problems, the need to solve them by making education play a decisive role in the life of any society and country is growing. A country that is not sufficiently engaged in the education of the young generation, in general, members of society, is doomed to stagnation and crisis. Because, in order to grow and develop in any society, the production of material and spiritual wealth must be constantly increasing. This means that the younger generation should rise to a higher level than their ancestors in creating material and spiritual wealth.

"The ideology of the new Uzbekistan that we are creating," says Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, "will be the idea of goodness, humanity, humanism." By ideology, we first of all mean education of thought, education of national and universal values. They are based on the concepts and values of our people that have been alive for thousands of years." At the heart of these updates is the fact that the spiritual reforms in a certain sense are having their effect.

Today, when the Republic of Uzbekistan is entering a new stage of development, special attention is being paid to the education system and new requirements are being developed. On this basis, on December 31, 2019, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Concept of continuous spiritual education and measures for its implementation" was adopted.

One of the priorities of the implementation of the concept of continuous spiritual education is to increase the knowledge and pedagogical culture of the population on child education, to regularly familiarize citizens with the effective methods and forms of implementation of continuous spiritual education.

The purpose of the concept is to gradually form age-appropriate social skills and qualities necessary for an independent and happy life in the young generation. To achieve this goal, to implement it in practice, it is necessary to perform the following tasks:

development of scientifically based indicators for evaluating spiritual and moral education;

development and implementation of the methodology of education, which starts from the period of pregnancy and lasts until adulthood, based on the principles of gradualism and continuity;

effective use of advanced achievements of national and modern pedagogy in child education;

to regularly improve the knowledge and skills of teachers along with students;

to establish a mechanism of effective cooperation between family, neighborhood and educational institutions, as well as mass media and other social structures in the formation of spiritual education;

spiritual education is based on the principles of gradual development and continuity.

The concept covers four stages:

the first stage: in families (fetal period, the period from birth to 3 years of age);

second stage: preschool education up to 3-6 (7) years;

third stage: general secondary education (primary class up to 7 (6)-10 years old, 11-17 (18) years old);

the fourth stage: young people who are active in production and are not employed, as well as in the system of secondary specialized professions and OTM.

In the conditions of new Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to spiritual development. Practical work in this regard has accelerated, especially in recent years. That is, the concept of systematization of spiritual education is being developed and put into practice. The social and spiritual map of the regions has been created.

If we analyze year by year, with the decision of the President of July 28, 2017 "On increasing the efficiency of spiritual and educational work and raising the development of the field to a new level", the Republic of Spiritual Promotion and the National scientific and practical centers of ideas and ideology were united, and on their basis, the Republican Spirituality and Enlightenment Center was established. These organizations developed scientific and practical researches, while the second one was engaged in promotion of these researches. Their goal is the same, that is, to thoroughly analyze and evaluate the current issues related to the national idea and ideology, today's complex ideological processes from a scientific and practical point of view, to determine the priority directions, and to explain them to different layers of the population. to learn the secret of our national interests, to reveal the nature of harmful ideas and ideological attacks that are contrary to our national interests, our way of life, to educate young people in love and loyalty to the Motherland, humanitarian qualities, the role of national customs, traditions and values in our lives and It consisted of holding conversations and meetings, educational events aimed at carrying out the importance of the event in all ways. Based on this decision, the status of the head of the center is equal to the minister, and the status of the deputy heads is equal to the deputy ministers. The issue of financing regional departments and divisions of the system from budget funds has been a problem for years, and the fact that its solution was established, and a separate building was allocated to accommodate the center and the organizations under its control, was a big change.

"Marifat" society of propagandists was established under the center, where mature propagandists who can influence the minds of the population gathered together. At present, it would be correct to say that this society is a huge "propaganda machine". This group is trying to promote the reforms implemented in all spheres today. It is commendable that the campaigners are supported and encouraged in every way.

Today, the center is considered the executive body of the Republican Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the leadership of the leaders in the direction of spirituality and enlightenment has made a big difference in the organization of propaganda work. In particular, the appointment of regional

leaders as responsible for the development of the sector shows a serious approach to the problems.

CONCLUSION. In the current systematic approach, the formation of social skills is planned in advance and the achievement of educational results is guaranteed. Therefore, the use of pedagogical technologies in the education of social skills in continuous spiritual education has become one of the innovative requirements. The continuous spiritual education system is a chain of pedagogical operations, tools, and methods to guarantee the effectiveness of gradual, continuous spiritual education of young people in family, pre-school, general secondary educational institutions. The President touched upon the bloody conflicts and conflicts in the regions of the world, and showed the need to strengthen the peace and tranquility in our country, to strengthen the fight against various threats, and also showed the simple ways of this fight that each of us can follow.

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